

Social Media Exposure Improves Students' Writing Skills in English 8

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Abstract:

Social media is a part of growing and parcel of our daily lives. As young generation have been interacting on social media on a constant basis, writing is one of the skills by means of which they interact. This research study aims to explore the potential of using social media to develop the students' writing skills. A survey was conducted to explore the tendency of using different tenets or forms of social media by English 8 students at Buburay National High School in Dimataling 2 District. School Year 2020-2021. The instrument used in this study was descriptive method and a survey questionnaire for the Social Media Exposure of the students. A Social Media exposure was carried out to compare students' English writing skill after discussion on Google meet or zoom to get depth information about students' attitude towards use of social media platforms. The results of survey point out that most students use and have easy access to social media through their gadgets.

The study found that using social media for lesson discussions helps students enhance their writing skills. Moreover, using social media in writing informative essays was an easy, motivating and interesting experience to use for writing practice. Most of the students were of the view that it is a new experience of learning writing by engaging in discussion with peers and teachers through using google meet platforms. However, this study employs the descriptive method design as a means of researching the reciprocity between social media use and the students' writing skills. The findings have indicated that students at Buburay National High School students' social media use habits exert significant impacts on the students' writing skills and the most these are susceptible to potential risks of the use of social media. The reported findings gave sufficient proof that social media is a convenient tool to develop better students' writing skills. Hence, social media literacy should be integrated into the curriculum.

Keywords: Social Media, Writing Skills, Accessibility, Analytical Thinking, Evaluation, Content Creation.

Introduction:

Information communication technologies are vital in all walks of life. In the world today, many people use various communication technologies, such as computer-aid Ed equipment, and the internet, People use social media as one tool to exchange ideas in their everyday communications. New technologies have impacted communication, enhanced social behavior, and promoted active learning and collaboration among students (Maloney, 2007). However few educators are also concerned about the negative impact of social media on students' academic performance and discourage its utilization in education (Brabazon, 2007). Pakistani social media/Facebook users are growing rapidly but the use of social media for educational purposes is little explored in Pakistan. Despite the popularity and incorporation of social media as a tool for language teaching inside and outside classroom, research on role of social media in Pakistani context focused on investigating the trends of its use among students and there is a lack of empirical research investigating the impact of using social media on language learning. In this scenario, it is necessary to conduct empirical research to examine the impact of using Facebook on students' writing skills. Can not be forced to learn until he has grown and developed to the point where he is ready for the learning experience (Eronico, 1990). Therefore, with this principle, a teacher should be considerate to his learners and flexible to the content of subject matter as far as composition- writing is concerned.

Given that millennials have been interacting on social media daily, writing is one of the skills by means of which they interact. Hence, there is a link between social media use and writing ability. Writing is an ability that is very often needed and an essential skill of academic success which merits special attention. Is a significant skill which plays a vital role in effective communication?

Achieving proficiency remains a challenging objective for most EFL students. Learned from an early age school, the act of writing enables success in academic and professional life. Employees' writing abilities are evaluated during recruitment processes and considered for advancement opportunities within the workplace. This crucial skill, therefore, requires greater attention and can be enhanced through social media platforms. Zheng, Yim & Warschauser (2018) highlight that "writing via social media can provide opportunities for English learners to communicate with native English speakers and practice their written language in authentic and motivating ways" (p. 1). Given the growing role of social media in education, writing via social media platforms becomes a rewarding experience over time. As far as (Zheng et al., 2018) are concerned, social media is a tool to assist learners for better understanding of the module and even parents who wish to help in the learning process of their children this time of pandemic and to answer the exercises in the module more accurately. This will lessen the burden of

In Buburay National High School particularly the Grade -VIII Students, English subject is one that obtains a low in writing performance. Now, the time learners, as well as the parents to facilitate easily their learning accomplishments in English writing performance of the students.

Literature Review:

Social media has emerged as a pervasive force in the daily lives of students, influencing how they communicate, access information, and engage in learning. The growth of social networking platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Google Meet has provided learners with opportunities to express themselves in written form, collaborate with peers, and receive feedback from teachers in real-time. These platforms, when harnessed effectively, can support the development of critical language skills, particularly writing, which is essential for academic success.

Writing is a fundamental skill in education, serving as a primary mode of communication and a measure of cognitive development. According to Axelrod and Cooper (1988), effective writing requires clarity, organization, and the ability to convey ideas logically. For English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students, achieving proficiency in writing is often challenging due to limited exposure to authentic language use and constrained practice opportunities. Social media provides a unique environment where learners can engage in meaningful writing experiences outside the traditional classroom, offering motivation and authentic contexts for communication.

Several studies have emphasized the role of social media in enhancing writing skills. Zheng, Yim, and Warschauer (2018) observed that writing through social media allows learners to communicate with native English speakers, practice language structures, and gain feedback in a motivating and interactive way. Choi (2008) highlighted that online collaboration through discussion forums and social networking sites improves ESL learners' coherence, organization, and expression in written tasks. Similarly, Ellison and Wu (2008) reported that blogging and social media participation encourage students to articulate ideas, reflect on content, and expand vocabulary, all of which are critical for academic writing development.

The development of social media literacy is crucial in leveraging these platforms for educational purposes. Masterman (2001) defines media literacy as the ability to interpret, analyze, evaluate, and create media messages critically. This literacy enables students to not only consume content but also produce meaningful written outputs. Hunges (2013) argued that students should be trained to analyze media content for accuracy, intent, and relevance, which directly contributes to improved writing skills. Therefore, social media exposure is most effective when combined with guided instruction and critical engagement, rather than unstructured or purely recreational use.

The tenets of media literacy—access, analysis, evaluation, and production—play a significant role in shaping students' writing competencies. Access refers to the ability to navigate digital platforms and retrieve relevant information, while analysis involves interpreting content and understanding its context. Evaluation allows students to make informed judgments about the credibility and relevance of information, and production emphasizes the creation and sharing of original content. By cultivating these competencies, educators can ensure that students' interaction with social media translates into enhanced writing performance (Hobbs, 2011).

Social media also offers practical benefits in the context of distance and modular learning, particularly during pandemic conditions. Zheng et al. (2018) noted that social media platforms provide flexibility and accessibility, allowing students to submit assignments, participate in discussions, and collaborate asynchronously. This accessibility reduces learning barriers, supports differentiated instruction, and encourages learners to engage in writing tasks with greater autonomy. Teachers can facilitate structured writing activities online, while students can practice composition and expression in a familiar and engaging environment.

However, literature also identifies challenges associated with social media use in education. Brabazon (2007) warned that overreliance on social media for informal communication may distract students from structured learning objectives. Madge, Meek, Wellens, and Hooley (2009) observed that students often use social networking primarily for socialization rather than academic engagement. These findings underscore the importance of deliberate instructional strategies that guide students toward purposeful writing activities while minimizing potential distractions inherent in digital platforms.

In the Philippine context, social media has become a widely used tool among students, yet its integration into formal education is still limited. Alcantara (2008) emphasized that while students are highly engaged online, structured interventions are necessary to channel this engagement toward educational outcomes, such as enhancing English writing skills. Luzana (2004) also highlighted that incorporating social media into lesson planning and writing exercises can provide learners with

opportunities to practice composition, express ideas, and receive constructive feedback, thereby improving overall writing competence.

Despite the potential of social media, empirical evidence on its direct impact on writing performance remains mixed. While students often demonstrate increased motivation and engagement when using online platforms, research indicates that frequency of use alone does not guarantee improved writing outcomes (Terantino & Graf, 2011). This suggests that educators must focus not only on accessibility but also on guided interaction, critical reflection, and scaffolded writing tasks to fully realize the educational benefits of social media.

In summary, the literature suggests that social media can serve as a valuable tool for developing students' writing skills, particularly in EFL contexts. Platforms such as Google Meet, Zoom, and Facebook provide authentic communication channels, opportunities for peer collaboration, and avenues for teacher feedback. When integrated with media literacy instruction that emphasizes access, analysis, evaluation, and production, social media can enhance students' composition skills, critical thinking, and engagement. While challenges remain in ensuring focused and purposeful use, carefully designed interventions have the potential to transform social media from a recreational activity into an effective educational resource, supporting the development of proficient and confident writers.

Research Questions

This study examined how social media affects the writing performance of English 8 students at Buburay National High School, Dimataling District 2, in the Division of Zamboanga del Sur.

Specifically, the study will answer the following questions, after the data had been gathered, analyzed, and interpreted.

1. To what level is students' media use, in terms of the following tenets?
 - 1.1. Access.
 - 1.2. Analysis.
 - 1.3. Evaluation; and
 - 1.4. Production?
2. To what level is the writing skill of students in terms of the following?
 - 2.1. Composition: 2.2. Informative Essay
3. Are there any significant relationship between the social media use or the nature of online activities that learners are engaged in and their students' writing skill performance?

Significance of the Study

The significance of the study lies in its capacity to bring into the surface valuable insights on the interfaces of social media exposure and students' writing skills.

Specifically, this study is seen as beneficial to the following individuals and groups that are considered the direct recipients of the results of this investigation.

Students. The results of this study will provide this group with some awareness on their weak points in using English in written communication. They will also become direct beneficiaries of whatever measures that the school will institute to improve their writing skill in English. Moreover, any improvement that teachers make on their teaching strategies shall directly benefit this group.

English Teachers. This group would be informed of the problems of students in written English communication, giving them opportunity to examine their capabilities in teaching effectively the skill to their students. This awareness will give rise and direction to be efforts to improve their level

of teaching effectiveness. The results of this study will also provide them with reliable feedback on the effectiveness of their teaching strategies and offer them insights that will help them revise their existing curricula in the teaching of English as a second language.

School Administrators. The results of this study would serve as the basis for this group to determine school activities necessary to help students in the use of the English language.

Parents. This study would provide an awareness to parents on the important role they play to help their students improve their communication skills in writing. The results of this study will also elicit support from parents by showing active involvement in their students' education.

Other Researchers. This group would also benefit from this study in terms of the results that this investigation will generate on the significant differences of the two variables the social media exposure and students' writing skill in English 8 at Buburay NHS.

Scope and Limitation

The scope and limitation of this study involved the following delimiting areas, which projected the parameters of the study to determine its contribution to the fund of knowledge in education, and find its rightful niche in the wide area of educational research.

Subject Matter. This study focusses on students' social media exposure and writing skills of the Grade 8 students of Buburay National High School and their significant differences and relationships.

Students' Social Media Exposure has the following predictors: access, analysis, evaluation, and production.

English writing skill uses the following type: informative essay.

Time and Place. This study was conducted at Buburay National High School, Buburay, Dimataling 2, Division of Zamboanga del Sur, during the school year 2021-2022.

Research Design. This study uses descriptive research design, employing surveys to collect data on students' social media exposure and tests to measure their writing skills.

Research Respondents. The research respondents of the study are Grade 8 Students of Buburay National High School. The students will answer the questionnaire on the use of Use social media and Writing Skill Performance. In determining the level of students' writing skills, they will ask to write informative essays. Their composition will rate by three raters who are themselves English teachers.

Research Instruments. Two sets of instruments are used in this study. The first instrument was a questionnaire oThe study's respondents are Grade 8 students from Buburay National High School. n Students' Social Media Exposure, which is source from Salandanan (2006).

The second instrument was a questionnaire on Students' Writing Skill Performance, which was used in the study of Alcantara (2008). This instrument was the ESL Grading Symbols used by the researcher in responding systematically to sentence-level errors, namely: global errors, local errors, and other errors are assigned corresponding weights as follows: global errors, 50%; local errors, 30%; and other errors, 20%, for a total of 100%, It was sourced from the study of Luzana (2004). The two instruments are considered standardized.

Statistical Treatment. The statistical treatment performed in this study will involve the descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics will establish the statuses of the three variables. The inferential statistics projected the significant differences of the two variables, using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), as well as the significant relationships between the independent variable and the dependent variable, using Pearson coefficient of correlation.

Research Methodology

This basic research utilized the descriptive type of research with the survey using questionnaires as the main process in gathering data on Social Media Exposure, and testing for students' writing skills.

Johnson and Christensen (2000) stated that the prime purpose of the descriptive study is to provide an accurate description or pictures of the status or characteristic of situation or phenomenon. This study also established the significant relationships of the variables, which in effect make this study descriptive-correlation research.

A. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

The sixty-nine (69) grade-VIII students of Buburay National High School for school year 2021-2022 are chosen to be the respondents of this research because it is the Grade level that the researcher handling. As the class adviser, she can efficiently monitor students' social media use and writing performance, and distribute survey questionnaires.

A. Data Gathering Methods

The researcher will first secure a permission to conduct this proposed study that aims to increase the Writing Performance in English 8 of Grade-VIII students in Buburay National High School. After approval is granted, a group of participants will be deliberately selected to determine whether this proposed strategy is effective. As an essential part of the data collection process, research participants will receive comprehensive information regarding the objectives and importance of the study, as well as their expected involvement and the measures in place to ensure confidentiality.

The first objective of this study is to examine the trend of using social media among Grade 8 students of Buburay National High School. A survey method is used for this purpose.

The first step to be done with this intervention is that pupils will be given first the ready-made questionnaires for them to answer. Afterwards, the researcher will get the total score of the students after the implementation of the said survey questionnaire given.

On the next week, the same set of students will be given with the said survey questionnaire along with the ready-made survey questionnaire in English to be answered. These answered survey questionnaires will be retrieved so scores will be obtained.

The two steps will be implemented during the first quarter to ensure reliable results for students.

Moreover, the researcher will only have one group to be focused considering that they are only 69 students, 39 females and 30 males. The researcher will be building a strong linkage to the parents of the respondents and orient them on what to do to ensure a reliable result of the study.

Then the two results will be compared to see if the result is reliable and given is helpful or really achieved the aim which is to increase the Writing skill of students in English 8.

a) Data Analysis Plan

To analyses and interpret the quantitative data, the paired sample t-test percentage statistic will be utilized as the appropriate analytical tool.

Standard Deviation

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \mu)^2}{N}}$$

where:

σ = population standard deviation

N = the size of the population
 x_i = each value from the population
 μ = the population means

Pearson product-moment correlation

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

where:

r = correlation coefficient
 x_i = values of the x-variable in a sample
 \bar{x} = mean of the values of the x-variable
 y_i = values of the y-variable in a sample
 \bar{y} = mean of the values of the y-variable

Discussion of Results and Recommendations

Students’ Media Exposure

This variable covers four main principles or learning opportunities offered by English teachers to enhance students' learning and social media engagement. This variable had considered following indicators, access, analysis, evaluation, and production.

Access. It involves the use of the full range of media and new technologies for receiving sending information through broadcast, cable, interactive. And other media forms. Table 1 shows the data for this sub variable.

Social Media Usage and Student’s Writing Performance

Table 1. Descriptive of Student’s Media Usage in terms of Access, Analysis, Evaluation and Production

	N	M	SD	QD
Access	69	3.08	0.23	<i>Often</i>
Analysis	69	3.06	0.30	<i>Often</i>
Evaluation	69	3.02	0.36	<i>Often</i>
Production	69	3.00	0.26	<i>Often</i>

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 = *Never*, 1.76 – 2.50 = *Seldom*, 2.51 – 3.25 = *Often*, 3.26 – 4.00 = *Always*; M – Mean,

SD – Standard Deviation, QD – Qualitative Description

Based on the results, the qualitative description of the Students’ Social Media Exposure

As presented in the table, the highest mean response

The results are explained by the actuality of their responses that the students are giving more importance on social media usage. This also shows that students' media access is sufficient to increase their understanding of the topic. The findings also indicate that students' use of social media has a significant impact on their daily lives. Moreover, it is evident in their responses since they really love watching shows, concerts, soap operas and other forms of entertainment on TV and even to musical programs on radio.

It also alludes that the students had not so much exposed by social media for discussion purposes and even maintaining networking on the worldwide web. It also shows that students lack access to computers or social media because there is not enough computer equipment to meet their needs.

The mean of Access is 3.08, Analysis is 3.06, Evaluation is 3.02 and Production is 3.00, interpreted as often is rated by the student’s respondents. The findings show that the access of the students in their social media usage is highly literate.

Analysis. This involves the ability to decipher the elements of social media messages and media systems, to understand their forms and functions, ownership and management, economic and policy implications, message, content, intent and effects, and decoding and re-conceptualizing their meanings.

This explains that the students are good enough in analyzing the social media literacy output. It also shows that students can identify facts and opinions through media literacy and analyze other aspects of media production.

According to Hunges (2013), students should have this ability to analyze for under this tenet, students can come to comprehend media messages like those sent through radio, cable, television internet, etc.

Evaluation. This actualizes the students’ ability to make judgments about the media, assess and apply journalistic ethics, critique elements and compare and contrast the values of media messages and systems to those of other personal and community value systems.

The study found that students frequently showed similar responses to social media exposure across access, analysis, evaluation, and production. This revealed that Social Media Exposure doesn’t have effects on the students’ writing skill. Hence, it could help the students in answering their given modules and other activities given by the teachers.

The findings for this, students garnered often. It also indicates that the students can do just enough especially selecting good media materials to enhance learning. They can even give enough reactions to commentaries and opinions that only mean they are good enough in evaluating the media usage.

Production. This stresses the ability of students to create messages in a variety of social media usage including text, video, and computer with a view toward sharing the results of this production with the larger community.

Therefore, social media exposure is about helping students become competent, critical and literate in all media forms so that they control the interpretation of what they see or hear rather than letting the interpretation control them. To become media literate is not to memorize facts or statistics about the media, but rather to learn to raise the right questions about what you are watching ,reading, or listening to; Len Masterman , the claimed author of Teaching the Media, calls it, “ critical autonomy” or the ability to think for oneself.

Table 2. Descriptive of Level of Student’s Writing Skills

	N	M	SD	QD
Writing Skills	69	81.01	2.85	<i>Very Good</i>

Legend: 50.00 % and Below - Very Poor, 50.00% - 59.99% - Poor, 60.00% - 69.99% -Fair, 70.00% - 79.99%

Good, 80.00% - 89.99% - Very Good, 90.00% – 100% - Excellent M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, QD – Qualitative Description

The students” Writing Skills refers to the ability of the students to write Informative Essay, which appreciated by these three Language Teachers. The results showed that the qualitative description of

Students' Writing Skills was very good, which had a mean of 81.01. This revealed that social media exposure didn't have effects on the students' writing skill. Therefore, it could help the students in answering their modules and other activities that were given by the teachers.

Table 2.2 Frequency and Percentage of Students' Writing Skills

Students' Writing Performance					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	73	1	1.4	1.4	1.4
	76	3	4.3	4.3	5.8
	77	3	4.3	4.3	10.1
	78	4	5.8	5.8	15.9
	79	11	15.9	15.9	31.9
	80	7	10.1	10.1	42.0
	81	9	13.0	13.0	55.1
	82	12	17.4	17.4	72.5
	83	7	10.1	10.1	82.6
	84	5	7.2	7.2	89.9
	85	2	2.9	2.9	92.8
	86	3	4.3	4.3	97.1
	87	1	1.4	1.4	98.6
	88	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
Total		69	100.0	100.0	

The general weighted average grades show that social media does not hinder students' writing skills; instead, it helps them improve by encouraging research, writing, and reading online information. The overall descriptive scores reached 100%.

Table 3. Correlation between Social Media Usage and Student's Writing Performance

Correlations			
		Overall Mean	Students Writing Performance
Social Media Usage Overall Mean	Pearson Correlation	1	-.042
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.730
	N	69	69
Students Writing Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.042	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.730	
	N	69	69

Correlation Coefficient Legend: 0.00 - ±0.19= *Slight; No or Almost No relationship*, ±0.20 - ±0.39 = *Low Correlation*; *Definite but small relationship*, ±0.40 - ±0.69 = *Moderate Correlation*; *Substantial relationship*, ±0.70 - ±0.89 = *High Correlation*; *Strong Relationship*, ±0.90 – 1.00 = *Very High Correlation, Very Dependable Relationship*

Pearson product correlation of social media usage and student's writing performance was found to be negative and not statistically significant ($r = -0.042$, $p > 0.05$). Hence, null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that social media usage does not affect students' writing performance.

Statistical Tool

Mean

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

where:

\bar{x} = mean

f = frequency

x = value of the sample

n = total frequency

$\sum x$ = sum of all the values

Standard Deviation

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \mu)^2}{N}}$$

where:

σ = population standard deviation

N = the size of the population

x_i = each value from the population

μ = the population means

Pearson product-moment correlation

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

where:

r = correlation coefficient

x_i = values of the x-variable in a sample

\bar{x} = mean of the values of the x-variable

y_i = values of the y-variable in a sample

\bar{y} = mean of the values of the y-variable

Conclusions

The following conclusions were reached by the researcher based on the strength of the findings on the interfaces of the two variables. This study found out that social media exposure and students' writing skills performance does not affect the students' writing skill, consequently modern technology revealed that students' easy to access, analyze, evaluate and produce output specifically in this pandemic time through social media networking, and it is potential tool to use in English Teaching to facilitate English learning. However, students have confidence to write with their own way and its motivates and engages students in this digital world. According to Terantino and Graf (2011) teachers' discussion with students and their comments on students posts on social media can enhance student teacher interaction. To sum up the major findings it can be said that using Social Media Platforms as medium for English teaching helps to develop positive attitudes and relationships, motivates students to participate, encourage a collaborative environment, helps to maintain better relationship between teacher and students.

Summary of Findings

The section outlines the findings on the two variables investigated, in the following order in the presentation of the research problems.

1. To what level is students' media use, in terms of the following tenets?

1.1. Access.

1.2. Analysis.

1.3. Evaluation; and

1.4. Production?

Students' Media Exposure was found to be often, with the overall mean of access was 3.08, the overall mean of analysis was 3.06, 3.02 for evaluation and production was 3.00.

2. To what level is the writing skill of students in terms of the following?

2.1. Composition: 2.2. Informative Essay

The Informative essay in students' writing skills was very good with the Mean of 81.01

3. Is there any significant relationship between the social media use or the nature of online activities that learners are engaged in and their students' writing skills performance?

No significant relationship was established between social media exposure and students' writing skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions reached in this research study, the researcher proposed the following recommendations:

Since the result of this study indicated significant differences in students' media exposure in the tenets of access, analysis, evaluation and production, the school management and teachers should take plan of action that will give opportunities to students' media literacy and practices to express, opinions and expressions based on their observations and personal reactions according to their level of understanding. The school included in this investigation should conduct more trainings for English teachers in guiding their students to become good writers most especially in the aspect of social media to be used by the teachers to enhance students' writing interest and improve their skill in expressing their own ideas.

No Significant relationship was established between social media Used, both school administrators and teachers should enhance strategies and intervention that would help increase the level of students writing skill.

No Significant relationship was not established between students' writing skills and student's social media usage and exposure. Yet, with this result teachers must strengthen their teaching strategies through students' interaction and collaboration in their learning activities. Researchers should carry out related studies in different settings to draw further conclusions about the relationship between the two variables and suggest actions for their development. This study will focus on 21st-century learning to design, refine, and encourage effective strategies to achieve this goal.

To the School administrators of Buburay NHS and the Department of Education to give an opportunities to the students to provide a free internet data connection and gadgets through they are experiencing a pandemic time so that they can easy to access their modular distance learning modality in order to equip the student who are excellent in their academic performance but they belong to a poor family it is a great challenge as an educator to please these kind of learners.

Dissemination and Advocacy Plans

Based on the findings of this research, dissemination and advocacy plans should be made. This study will be disseminated to the school for implementation. The result of the study will be disseminated through research presentations in faculty and staff meetings or in LAC session in Buburay National High School and to Dimataling districts, for them to be aware of the problems faced by the parents in coaching their children in modular distance learning.

Further, this study will help the teachers and the department to craft an intervention that will address the problem experienced during the modular distance learning.

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